

Perceived Service Quality of Intercity Bus Transport Services Provided in Owerri Metropolis of Imo State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The provision of intercity bus transport service is one of the backbones of any emerging city. However, its mere provision will not fulfill the public transportation needs as it is unlikely to be utilised if the service quality does not meet the expectations of commuters. This study assessed the perceived service quality of intercity bus transport services provided in Owerri metropolis, Imo State. Convenience sampling method was used to administer questionnaires to 390 passengers, waiting to be boarded, in each of the 24 selected intercity bus transport service companies. Frequency table and Gap scores in SERVQUAL model were used to analyse the data. The study revealed that about 52% of the respondents had preference for two bus companies, ABC and Good Shepherd Motors. Short travel time majorly accounted for their choice. The study found negative gaps in all the five dimensions of service quality. Tangible dimension of service quality had the highest gap score (-1.19) while reliability recorded the lowest (-0.56). Conclusively, intercity bus transport services provided in Owerri metropolis did not meet the expectations of respondent commuters. The study recommends routine vehicle checks by operators; electronic display of bus service timetables and fares; and ticketing system being easily accessible in terms of location and operating hours.

Keywords: bus, intercity, perceived, service quality

Introduction

Cities are centres of economic, social, political and environment livability occupying a pride of place in policy formulations, by city administrator and policy makers (Ogunkoya, 2008). The expansion of the cities coupled with increasing urban population, has resulted in greater demand for movement for various purposes. This movement from one place to another through public transport system forms part of the day-to-day activities of most individuals in the developed and developing countries (Wojuade and Badiora, 2017). The movement of people within a city is called intracity movement whereas movement between cities is intercity, and covers both short and long distances.

The concept of intercity originated from the intercity sector of British Rail and includes long-distance travels of over 100km between cities, towns or regions or states (Kato

et al., 2010). Ojo *et al.*, (2014) posited that intercity transport is responsible for connecting cities, aligning towns and villages by a network of service. Intercity bus concept came from Carl Eric Wickman, when in 1913, he was fed up with his inability to sell a seven-passenger automobile on the showroom floor of the dealership where he worked. He then started using it to transport miners between Hibbing and Alice, Minnesota, United States (Woldeamonuel, 2012 cited in Ojo *et al.*, 2014). This was later used to provide service regularly in what started as a new company (Greyhound) and industry.

Intercity buses are regularly scheduled bus services for the public that operate with limited stops over fixed routes, connecting two or more urban areas not in close proximity, and that make meaningful connections with scheduled intercity bus service to more distant

points, if such service is available (Federal Transit Administration [FTA] 2007; David *et al.*, 2011). According to Mudenda and Guga (2017), an intercity bus carries passengers over significant distances between cities, towns or other populated areas, unlike a municipal bus, with frequent stops throughout a city or town.

The intercity bus transport service is very important for cities, in particular, emerging ones. When people use intercity bus transport service instead of their private cars, environmental as well as noise pollution is reduced, hence the need for its provision. However, the mere provision of intercity bus transport services and infrastructure will not themselves fulfill the public transportation needs, and is unlikely to be utilized if the service quality does not meet the expectations of users.

Service quality is a concept that has aroused considerable interest and debates in the research literature because of the difficulties in both defining and measuring it with no overall consensus emerging (Wisniewski, 2001). Lewis and Mitchel (1990) stated that service quality is the extent to which a service meets passengers' needs or expectations. It is the difference between passengers' expectations of service and perceived service. If expectations are greater than performance, then perceived quality is lesser than satisfactory, hence passengers' dissatisfaction occurs. Freitas (2013) stated that increasing requirements from customers concerning service quality put to check the service provided by intercity bus companies and can further contribute to the proliferation of competitors. The improvement in service quality as a tool for better profitability does not mean investing in advanced technologies alone, but also prioritizing actions that influence the quality level perceived by customers, resulting in more attractive services.

SERVQUAL is a model developed by Parasuraman *et al.* (1985) which is used to

measure passengers' perceived service quality. The instrument is based on five distinct dimensions for comparison (gap) between passengers' expectations and actual service experienced. The five dimensions are: (i) "reliability" which refers to the ability to perform the promised service, dependably and accurately; (ii) "assurance" which involves the knowledge and courtesy of employees, and their ability to inspire trust and confidence; (iii) "tangibles", representing the appearance of physical factors such as equipment, facilities and personnel; (iv) "empathy" which is providing individual attention and care to passengers and (v) "responsiveness", that is, the willingness to provide help and prompt service to passengers.

This study employs a modified SERVQUAL instrument to measure the service quality of intercity bus transport service from the passengers' perception. Service quality was measured on the basis of the twenty-five (25) points which constitute the five dimensions of service quality.

Several authors have, at different times, used SERVQUAL to measure service quality and customer satisfaction. For instance, a study by Dyah *et al.* (2013) on the service satisfaction of intercity bus based on tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy dimensions of service quality revealed that passengers' dissatisfaction majorly covered points such as: facilities in the bus, departure and arrival punctuality, ability to assist customers with difficulties, among others.

Again, passengers' perceived service quality was largely poor on the Cape Coast—Accra route in Ghana, as they were not satisfied with 15 out of 26 SERVQUAL attributes rated (Ojo *et al.*, 2014) The study reiterated the need for bus companies to improve their services for more passenger satisfaction. A similar study by Ali (2014) on passengers' satisfaction, vis-à-vis intra-city public bus transport services in Abuja,

revealed that most passengers were not satisfied with the quality of service rendered.

Owerri metropolis is one of the emerging cities in Nigeria, and is the administrative, commercial and educational centre of Imo State. Majority of the residents depend on intercity bus transport services to fulfill their transport needs. Within the state, there are several public and private companies providing and operating intercity bus transport services. Recently, most of the companies began improving their service quality in order to improve their business performance. However, with the improved service quality comes increase in service costs. This study is, therefore, aimed at assessing passengers' perception of service quality provided by intercity bus transport services in Owerri metropolis.

Materials and Method

The Study Area

Owerri metropolis politically consists of Owerri West, Owerri North, and Owerri Municipal Local Government Areas [LGAs]. It lies within latitude $6^{\circ} 15'$ - $6^{\circ} 34'$ of the Equator and longitude $6^{\circ} 51'$ - $7^{\circ} 15'$ of the Greenwich Meridian. It is bounded to the east by Aboh Mbaise LGA, to the west by Ohaji/Egbema LGA; and the north by Mbatoli and Ikeduru LGAs, while Ngor Okpala LGA lie to the south (Figure 1). The study area covers an area of about 555.6sq km. The area is characterized by wet and dry seasons associated with the movement of Inter Tropical Convergence zone [ITCZ], north and south of equator (Ibe, 2009). The dry season occurs from November to March, with a spell of coolness and dry dusty Harmattan wind that is mostly felt in December and January. The wet season occurs between April and September (Umunnakwe, 1999).

Figure 1: Study Area
Source: Administrative Map of Imo State

According to the National Population Commission (2009), Owerri metropolis had a population of about 403,425 people (197,944 males and 205,481 females). The projected population for Owerri, using exponential formula at 3.35% inter-census growth rates, for the year

2018, gave a total population 603,044. Owerri metropolis is predominantly inhabited by the Igbos, a major ethnic group in southern Nigeria. There are also other ethnic groups like

the Ibibio, Efik, Yoruba, Hausa, and Idoma who migrated to the study area for the purpose of economic prosperity. The economic activities of the people are primarily agriculture, commerce and civil service (Olayemi, 1998; Olaitan, 2006; Oladeebo, 2008). Major cash crops grown include oil palm, raffia palm, rice, groundnut, melon, cotton, cocoa, rubber, maize, etc. Food or subsistence crops such as yam, cassava, cocoyam and maize are also produced in large quantities (Unaeze and Anyanwu, 2017). These economic activities require movement to and from Owerri which makes intercity transport a necessity. Intercity transport companies include Imo Mass Transit, Abia Line Network Transit Limited, Rivers Transport Company, ABC Transport, Benn Way Links, Cross Country Transport Company and Ekeson Transport Company Limited, amongst others.

Methods

According to Churchill and Iacobucci (2004), one-third of a total study population can suffice for an empirical research. This study adopted this approach in its selection of the number of intercity bus transport service operators surveyed. With seventy (70) registered intercity bus service operators, one-third was selected, giving a total of twenty-four (24). This consisted of three (3) public and twenty-one (21) private-owned intercity bus transport services. The selection ensured adequate understanding of intercity bus transport service utilization and customer satisfaction with regards to service quality in the study area.

The study population estimated that 15,357 passengers moved daily via the 24 selected intercity bus transport companies. Yamane's formula (1967) was used to derive the sample size of 390 respondents. For questionnaire administration, convenience sampling was employed on the 390 passengers, as they waited to board the selected intercity

bus services. This ensured that respondents were only passengers who patronized the selected intercity bus services, thus, enhancing the reliability of data used for the study.

Descriptive statistics, namely, frequency table and Gap scores in SERVQUAL were used in the determination of the service quality gap. SERVQUAL measures the gap between customer expectations and perceptions in terms of five dimensions namely, tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy, measured using 5-point likert scale. Buttle (1996) stated that the gap score is arrived at by the averages of either for each of the attribute (Perception (P)-Expectation (E) divided by one), dimension by dimension analysis $((P_1+P_2+P_3+\dots +P_n) - (E_1+E_2+E_3+\dots +E_n)/n)$, where P_1 to P_n , and E_1 to E_n , represent the perception and expectation statements relating to a single dimension. The greater the gap score calculated as $G = P-E$, the higher the score for perceived service quality. Also, a negative gap score indicates that passengers perceived that service quality did not meet their expectations while positive gap score indicates that passengers perceived that service quality exceeded their expectations.

Results and Discussion

Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

The demographic characteristics of the respondents include the sex, age, marital status, religion and tribe. Table 1 revealed that 53.3% of the respondents are males while 46.7% are females. This implies that more male commuters patronize intercity bus services than their female counterparts. It was also revealed that 50.3% of the respondents were in the age range 20-39 years, followed by 40-59 years (32.3%) while the least were 60 years and above (4.9). This is an indication that youths tend to patronize intercity bus transport services the most. This can be attributed to

their adventurous nature, as well as agility and willingness to explore and travel to various places, to engage in different activities and search for better economic opportunities. The reverse can be said of people above 60 years of age, perhaps due to being less agile thus reducing their enthusiasm for long-distance traveling. Data on the marital status of respondents revealed that 50.3% were single, whereas 43.3% were married. The result on the marital status indicates that a higher number of

singles engage in intercity movements which may be due to lesser familial commitments, synonymous with marriage. In terms of religion, 89.5% were Christians, 7.4% Muslims and 3.1% traditionalists. This was not unexpected as the population in the study area is predominantly Christians. The tribal/ethnicity distribution of the respondents revealed that 68.5% were Igbos, followed by Yoruba (17.2%) while Hausa/Fulani accounted for the least, being 4.6%.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male	208	53.3
Female	182	46.7
Total	390	100.0
Age (years)		
Less than 20	48	12.3
20-39	197	50.5
40-59	126	32.3
Over 59	19	4.9
Total	390	100.0
Marital status		
Married	169	43.3
Single	196	50.3
Widowed	15	3.8
Divorced	10	2.6
Total	390	100.0
Religion		
Islam	29	7.4
Christianity	349	89.5
Traditional	12	3.1
Total	390	100.0
Tribe/Ethnicity		
Igbo	267	68.5
Yoruba	67	17.2
Hausa/Fulani	18	4.6
Others	38	9.7
Total	390	100.0

Source: Authors Survey, 2019

Socio-Economic Characteristics of Respondents

The socio-economic characteristics of the respondents include educational level, occupation, income, and household size. Table 2 revealed that 55.1% had tertiary level education,

33.1% had secondary while 1.5% had no formal education. The distribution implies that majority of the respondents are literate and able to respond soundly, providing the study with adequate information.

Also, Table 2 revealed that 35.1% of the respondents are engaged in trading/business, 32.1% are civil servants, while other forms of occupations such as artisans account for 18.7%. The higher number of traders and civil servants that patronize intercity bus services in the study area is due to the increasing need for transferability of goods and services, as well as the need for transportation of workers to their offices located outside the city.

Table 2: Socio-Economic Characteristics of Respondents

Educational Level	Frequency	Percentage
No formal education	6	1.5
Primary school	40	10.3
Secondary school	129	33.1
Tertiary	215	55.1
Total	390	100.0
Occupation		
Civil service	73	32.1
Trader/business	137	35.1
Farming	37	9.5
House wife	18	4.6
Others	125	18.7
Total	390	100.0
Monthly Income		
Less than ₦20000	90	23.1
₦20000 - ₦39999	134	34.4
₦40000 - ₦59999	85	21.7
₦60000 - ₦79999	42	10.8
₦80000 and Above	28	7.2
No Fixed Income	11	2.8
Total	390	100.0

Source: Authors Survey, 2019

Also, income is a major determinant of standard of living. As revealed in Table 2, on a monthly basis, 34.4% of the respondents earn between ₦20000 - ₦39999; 23.1% earn less than ₦20000; 21.7% earn ₦40000 - ₦59999; 10.8% earn ₦60000 - ₦79999; and 7.2% earn ₦80000 and above. The respondents' level of income might be connected with high educational status of the respondents which in most cases determine their income. Although transportation to some commuters is a necessity, respondents' income level often

influences their choices of mode of transportation.

Preference for Intercity Bus Transport Service Company

Table 3 shows that 51.8% of the respondents have preference for certain companies while 48.2% do not have any preferred bus company. The preference for particular companies is as a result of passengers' perceived quality of service rendered by each company. On preferred bus transport companies, 41.6% of the respondents

prefer ABC, 14.4% prefer Good Shepherd Motors, and 12.8% prefer Nothing Pass God,

while the least number of respondents prefer Faith Travelers and Tour (0.8%).

Table 3: Preferred Intercity Bus Company

Prefer particular Intercity Company	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	202	51.8
No	188	48.2
Total	390	100.0
Name of preferred intercity company		
ABC	84	41.6
Abia State Transport limited	13	6.4
Benn Way Links	16	7.9
Blessed Edison	3	1.5
Constant Links	2	1.0
Ekeson Transport	3	1.5
Faith Travelers and Tour	1	0.5
God is Good	4	2.0
Good Shepherd Motors	29	14.4
Imo State City Transport	8	4.0
Jesus Lord Motors	5	2.5
Nothing Pass God	26	12.8
Port Harcourt Transport Company Limited	2	1.0
Young Shall Grow	6	2.9
Total	202	100.0

Source: Authors Survey, 2019

Table 4: Reason for preferred intercity Company

Reason for Preference	Frequency	Percentage
Cheap fare	16	7.9
Comfortable seat	22	10.9
Competence of the driver	8	4.0
Courtesy behaviour of the bus company staff	5	2.5
Easy to access park	2	1.0
Reliable and comfort	28	13.9
Good physical condition of buses	29	14.3
Good security	5	2.5
Provide timely and efficient services	9	4.5
Safety and trained drivers	29	14.3
Short travel time	49	24.2
Total	202	100.0

Source: Authors Survey, 2019

Reasons for Preference of an Intercity Bus Transport Service Company

There are several factors responsible for passengers' choice of preferred bus

companies. These are indicated in Table 4. It was observed that 24.2% had their preferences due to short travel time. This was followed by 14.3%, whose preferences were due to safety and trained drivers, or good physical conditions of the buses. 13.9% preferred some companies as a result of their reliability and comfort, while the least (1%) were respondents who preferred the companies due to easy access to the motor parks. The result shows that most commuters will prefer to spend lesser time in the bus parks, no matter the facilities and services offered. This helps commuters reduce travel time. Additionally, time spent on travel is dependent on several factors such as the bus company's speed limit, nature of road, traffic flow, take-off time and nature of vehicle. This confirms why other preferences were either safety and trained drivers or good physical conditions of the buses.

Service Quality of Intercity Bus Transport Service Company

Service quality is a function of the users' expectations-perceptions gap (Govender and Pan, 2011). The difference between expectations and perceptions is called

the gap which is the determinant of customers' perception of service quality. Service quality in general, consists of five distinct dimensions: tangibles (physical facilities, equipment, appearance of personnel); reliability (ability to perform the promised service dependably and accurately), responsiveness (willingness to help customers and provide prompt service), assurance (knowledge and courtesy of employees and their ability to inspire trust and confidence), and empathy (caring or the individualized attention a firm provides its customers) (Budiono, 2009). These five variables are subsequently assessed.

Tangibles dimension

As depicted in Table 5, neat ticket office had the highest expectation score of 4.85, with the lowest expectation score applying to adequate in-bus facilities (4.42). The highest perception score related to having technically sound buses (3.78) and the lowest perception score was staff being neatly-dressed and on uniform. The largest gap score (-1.80) pertained to the staff being neatly-dressed and on uniform, while the lowest gap score (-0.75) was in respect to having technically sound buses.

Table 5: Tangibles Dimension

Factors	Expectation (E)	Perception (P)	Gap
	Mean	Mean	(P – E)
Ticket office/loading point being attractive	4.45	3.35	-1.10
Adequate space in ticket office	4.46	3.49	-0.97
Neat ticket office	4.85	3.31	-1.54
Staff neatly-dressed and on uniform	4.43	2.63	-1.80
Have technically sound buses	4.53	3.78	-0.75
Adequate in-bus facilities	4.42	3.43	-0.99

Source: Authors Analysis, 2019

Table 6: Reliability Dimension

Factors	Expectation (E)	Perception (P)	Gap
	Mean	Mean	(P – E)
Timely arrival and departure	4.93	3.49	-1.44
Bus breakdown in transit	1.93	2.57	0.64
Easy booking and payment at all times	4.18	3.81	-0.37
Error-free bus time-table	4.27	3.56	-0.71
Good/accurate recording of passenger data	4.55	3.61	-0.94

Source: Authors Analysis, 2019

Reliability dimension

Regarding the reliability dimension, Table 6 revealed that timely arrival and departure had the highest expectation score (4.93), with the lowest expectation score being bus breakdown in transit (1.93). The highest perception score pertained to easy booking and payment at all times (3.81), with bus breakdown in transit having the lowest perception score (2.57). The largest gap score (-1.44) pertained to timely arrival and departure, while the lowest gap score (0.64) was in respect to bus breakdown in transit.

Responsiveness dimension

As indicated in Table 7, as far as expectations were concerned, providing timely and efficient services scored the highest (4.40), while clear and helpful communication with passengers scored the lowest (4.29). The highest perception score pertained to informing passengers on change in bus time and prices in advance (3.84), while clear and helpful communication with passengers had the lowest perception score (3.48). The lowest gap score (-0.49) pertained to informing passengers on change in bus time and price in advance, while the largest gap score (-0.81) was in respect to clear and helpful communication with passengers.

Table 7: Responsiveness Dimension

Factors	Expectation (E)	Perception (P)	Gap
	Mean	Mean	(P – E)
Inform passengers on change in bus time and price in advance	4.33	3.84	-0.49
Provide timely and efficient services	4.40	3.83	-0.57
Clear and helpful communication with passengers	4.29	3.48	-0.81

Source: Authors Analysis, 2019

Table 8: Assurance Dimension

Factors	Expectation (E)	Perception (P)	Gap
	Mean	Mean	(P – E)
Passengers feel safe transacting with ticket staff	4.78	3.63	-1.15
Friendliness of staff both in-bus and at the office	4.29	3.40	-0.89
Staff know their job descriptions	4.42	3.91	-0.51
Security and safety of passengers/luggage is guaranteed	4.56	3.72	-0.84
Drivers are experienced	4.78	4.15	-0.63
Behaviour of staff instill confidence in passengers	4.28	3.49	-0.79

Source: Authors Analysis, 2019

Assurance dimension

As indicated in Table 8, passengers feeling safe transacting with ticket staff and experienced drivers each had the highest expectation scores (4.78), with the lowest expectation score pertaining to behaviour of staff to instill confidence in passengers (4.28). The highest perception score was related to drivers being experienced (4.15). Friendliness of staff in the confines of the bus and at the office both scored the lowest perception of 3.40 each. The lowest gap score (-0.51) pertained to bus staff knowledge of their job descriptions, while the largest gap score (-1.15) was in respect to passengers feeling safe transacting with the ticket staff.

Empathy dimension

The findings from Table 9 indicate that, as regards empathy, the highest expectation score applied to operating hours being convenient for passengers (4.34) with the lowest expectation score applying to two items, viz. ease of accessing ticket office, and staff providing individualized attention to assist passengers (4.20). The lowest perception score was recorded on staff providing individualized attention to assist passengers (3.12) and the highest perception score related to operating hours being convenient for passengers (3.76). The lowest gap score (-0.58) pertained to staff seeking after the best interest of passengers and operating hours being convenient for passengers. The largest gap score (-1.14) was in respect to ease in getting service information through SMS and telephone.

Table 9: Empathy Dimension

Factors	Expectation (E)	Perception (P)	Gap
	Mean	Mean	(P – E)
Staff seeking after the best interest of passengers	4.22	3.64	-0.58
Operating hours are convenient for passengers	4.34	3.76	-0.58
Easy to get service information through SMS and telephone	4.28	3.14	-1.14
Ease of accessing ticket office	4.20	3.57	-0.63
Staff provide individualized attention to assist passengers	4.20	3.12	-1.08

Source: Authors Analysis, 2019

Table 10: Comparison of the Service Quality Dimensions

Dimension	Expectation (E)	Perception (P)	Gap
	Mean	Mean	(P – E)
Tangibles	4.52	3.33	-1.19
Reliability	3.97	3.41	-0.56
Responsiveness	4.34	3.72	-0.62
Assurance	4.52	3.72	-0.80
Empathy	4.23	3.45	-0.78

Source: Authors Analysis, 2019

Comparison of the service quality dimensions

Table 10 provides the mean expectation and perception scores as well as the gaps, with regards to the five service quality dimensions. In terms of expectation, tangibles and assurance were rated as the highest (4.52) each, and reliability was the lowest (3.97). Regarding perception, responsiveness and assurance were the highest (3.72 each), with tangibles being the lowest (3.33).

The gap scores reveal that tangibles have the largest gap score (-1.19), with reliability having the lowest (-0.56). Generally speaking, the quality of service provided by intercity bus transport operators in Owerri metropolis did not meet the expectations of commuters. This contradicts the work of Nkyami (2016), where the researcher observed a positive gap in the measurement of service quality in bus services operating between Dar

es Salaam and Morogoro, two capital cities in Tanzania. However, Nkyami (2016) observed that tangibles dimension was the highest perceived service quality that did not meet the expectations of the commuters.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study assessed the perceived service quality of intercity bus transport services in Owerri metropolis, Imo State. It revealed that youths are the major patrons of intercity bus services. Further, it found that the quality of intercity bus transport services provided by the various operators did not meet commuters' expectations. Based on the findings, the following are recommended: routine vehicle checks by intercity bus transport operators; display of service timetables and fares electronically; and better accessibility of ticketing system, in terms of location and operating hours.

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